

Vector Quantization-Based Opportunistic Semantic Communication for Object Detection

Hyeseong Yun, Seungeun Oh, and Seong-Lyun Kim
Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Yonsei University

Abstract—This paper proposes a communication-efficient generative AI framework for object detection through semantic communication. Specifically, the network consists of a transmitter (Tx) and a receiver (Rx), each equipped with the encoder and decoder of a VQ-VAE-2 model. The raw image observed at the Tx is compressed into discrete codebook indices, which are then transmitted to the Rx, where they are decoded and used to determine the presence or absence of an object. While transmitting discrete representations instead of raw images improves communication efficiency, this alone is insufficient to meet the stringent latency and bandwidth requirements of time-critical object detection. To further enhance communication efficiency, we propose an opportunistic semantic communication scheme that employs thresholding based on the distributional distance between the codebook index distributions of samples with and without target objects. Furthermore, we formulate an optimization problem to minimize the object detection error under a given communication budget by tuning this threshold. Numerical evaluations corroborate that our method achieves only 45.65% of the transmission cost compared to its full-transmission counterpart, while preserving 99.98% SSIM and improving PSNR to 101.28%, thereby validating the effectiveness of the proposed opportunistic transmission strategy.

Index Terms—Semantic communication, VQ-VAE, object detection, opportunistic transmission, generative AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Emerging applications in surveillance, monitoring, and communication increasingly rely on visual data collected by resource-constrained devices (e.g., edge or IoT devices). In such scenarios, transmitting high-resolution images or even compressed representations of all captured samples can lead to significant communication overhead, particularly in bandwidth-limited wireless environments. However, not all captured images are equally informative—many contain little to no meaningful content, and only some are worth transmitting under limited bandwidth [1].

Conventional image transmission methods such as JPEG compression or Deep joint source–channel coding (Deep JSCC) [2] apply uniform encoding and transmission regardless of semantic importance. Recent advances in semantic communication explore transmitting information that preserves meaning rather than raw data. However, most existing methods either transmit all semantic features without discrimination or require retraining the entire encoder-decoder architecture with task-specific supervision, limiting their practicality in general-purpose deployment. In contrast, our method maintains a general-purpose encoder and only uses lightweight statistical supervision to estimate semantic importance, allowing efficient adaptation without retraining the model itself.

To address this gap, we propose a selective image transmission framework that leverages semantic importance estimation at the latent representation level. Built upon the hierarchical VQ-VAE-2 model [3], our system compresses input images into discrete codebook indices and evaluates their semantic significance by analyzing the distribution of codebook indices. We compute a semantic importance score using total variation distance (TVD) between the latent codebook PMF of a sample and class-average distributions. Based on this score, only semantically meaningful samples are transmitted, reducing communication cost without sacrificing key information.

A threshold for selection is optimized using a Lagrangian formulation to balance transmitting fewer samples and avoiding omission of meaningful content. Importantly, our method requires no retraining and operates without ground-truth labels during deployment, making it broadly applicable and easy to integrate into existing systems.

We demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach on the Singapore Maritime Dataset [4]. Experimental results show that our method achieves high semantic validity (93.3%) and semantic retention (84.9%), while reducing the average transmission rate by 54.5% compared to standard baselines. Moreover, our system preserves competitive image reconstruction quality (PSNR: 32.54 dB, SSIM: 0.9092) with significantly lower transmission latency.

In summary, our contributions are as follows:

- We propose a semantic importance estimation method using VQ-VAE-2 codebook distributions and total variation distance.
- We formulate a Lagrangian-based threshold optimization strategy to trade off preserving important content and avoiding unnecessary transmissions.
- We present a general-purpose, task-agnostic selective transmission framework that significantly reduces communication cost while preserving essential image semantics.
- We validate our method on a realistic, high-resolution maritime dataset, demonstrating its effectiveness in reducing transmission load while preserving essential content.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a semantic communication system in which an IoT or edge device transmits compressed images to a remote server using a shared encoder-decoder model. The goal is to minimize communication overhead while preserving semantic fidelity.

Fig. 1. Overall architecture of the proposed semantic communication system with VQ-VAE-2 and importance-aware selective transmission.

A. Semantic Communication Framework

At each time step t , the device captures an image $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$, which is processed by a semantic encoder $f_1(\cdot)$ and a channel encoder $f_2(\cdot)$. The resulting signal s_t is transmitted over a noisy channel:

$$\mathbf{y}_t = \mathbf{H}f_2(f_1(x_t)) + \mathbf{n}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{H} denotes the channel matrix and $\mathbf{n} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I})$ is additive noise. The receiver reconstructs the image via channel and semantic decoders:

$$\hat{x}_t = g_1(g_2(\mathbf{y}_t)). \quad (2)$$

This end-to-end system is designed to preserve the semantic content of x_t while reducing transmitted data.

B. Hierarchical VQ-VAE-2 Architecture

The semantic encoder and decoder are implemented using a hierarchical VQ-VAE-2 [3], which extracts semantic features at two levels: a top-level latent map $z_{\text{top}} \in \mathbb{Z}^{h \times w}$ for global structure, and a bottom-level map $z_{\text{bottom}} \in \mathbb{Z}^{h' \times w'}$ for fine details. Each is quantized using a separate codebook $\mathcal{E} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times D}$.

The model is trained to minimize:

$$\mathcal{L} = \|x - \hat{x}\|_2^2 + \|\text{sg}[\mathbf{z}_e] - \mathbf{z}_q\|_2^2 + \beta \|\text{sg}[\mathbf{z}_q] - \mathbf{z}_e\|_2^2, \quad (3)$$

where $\text{sg}[\cdot]$ denotes the stop-gradient operator and β balances the commitment loss.

After training, each image is encoded into index maps z_{top} and z_{bottom} , which are flattened and losslessly converted into binary streams for transmission. In our setup (224×224 input), the top-level code accounts for 20% and the bottom-level for 80% of the bitstream. The receiver recovers these indices and reconstructs the image using the decoder.

This VQ-VAE-based semantic representation significantly reduces data size while retaining the core content necessary for high-quality reconstruction.

C. Wireless Channel Model

To model transmission latency, we consider a wireless channel with bandwidth W and a time-varying signal-to-noise ratio $SNR(t)$. Let d_s denote the amount of information (in bits) required to transmit a single semantic sample (i.e., one image). This is given by:

$$d_s = (|z_{\text{top}}| + |z_{\text{bottom}}|) \cdot \lceil \log_2 K \rceil \quad (\text{in bits}), \quad (4)$$

where K is the codebook size.

If B_s is the number of semantic samples transmitted per second (i.e., image throughput), then the total bit rate is:

$$L_t = d_s \cdot B_s. \quad (5)$$

Accordingly, the transmission latency can be expressed using Shannon's capacity formula:

$$T(t) = \frac{L_t}{W \log_2(1 + SNR(t))} = \frac{d_s \cdot B_s}{W \log_2(1 + SNR(t))}, \quad (6)$$

which captures the dependency of latency on both the semantic bit cost per sample and the sample transmission rate. In our latency analysis, we assume a constant sample rate B_s across all methods and focus on the variation in d_s resulting from selective transmission.

Although the original image $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$ is compressed into a compact discrete representation of size d_s bits via the VQ-VAE encoder, the resulting transmission load can still be substantial in scenarios with constrained bandwidth or high-density device deployments. In such cases, even the compressed bitstream may saturate the available channel capacity, leading to increased latency and degraded system performance.

To further alleviate this bottleneck, we propose a semantic importance-based selective transmission strategy. By quantifying the semantic importance of each input sample and transmitting only those deemed critical, our method significantly reduces the transmission burden while preserving essential information—without requiring any task-specific model re-training.

III. SEMANTIC IMPORTANCE-BASED OPPORTUNISTIC TRANSMISSION

Fig. 1 shows the overall architecture of the proposed semantic communication system. It is built upon a hierarchical VQ-VAE-2 model and incorporates a semantic importance estimation module—denoted as the selection module in the figure—which selectively transmits meaningful content based on the latent codebook distribution.

To further enhance transmission efficiency under constrained resources, we introduce a semantic importance-based selective transmission framework. The core idea is to evaluate the semantic importance of each image based on its latent codebook distribution and selectively transmit only those that are deemed critical. Our method operates entirely on the VQ-VAE latent space without requiring additional task-specific supervision or retraining.

Unlike conventional semantic communication frameworks that transmit all compressed representations indiscriminately, our approach enables a selective transmission strategy guided by semantic importance.

A. Semantic Importance Estimation and Threshold-Based Selection

To determine whether an input image x_t is semantically meaningful, the encoder computes a semantic importance score D_t that quantifies the importance of the sample. In this study, the top-level latent representation z_{top} , which captures global semantic features of the image, is utilized to assess importance. Let p_{x_t} denote the empirical probability mass function (PMF) over the top-level codebook indices derived from z_{top} at the t -th time slot.

To supervise the estimation of semantic importance, we assign binary labels $y_t \in \{0, 1\}$ based on object presence: images containing identifiable objects beyond the static background (e.g., vessels, structures) are labeled as $y_t = 1$, while background-only scenes are labeled as $y_t = 0$. Using these labels, we compute class-average PMFs: let μ_+ and μ_- represent the average distributions over codebook indices for important and unimportant samples, respectively. The semantic importance score is defined as:

$$D_t = \text{TVD}(p_{x_t}, \mu_+) - \text{TVD}(p_{x_t}, \mu_-), \quad (7)$$

where $\text{TVD}(p, q) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i |p_i - q_i|$ denotes the total variation distance (TVD) between two discrete distributions [5].

The use of TVD in defining D_t provides a convenient mathematical property: the triangle inequality. Specifically, for any three distributions p, q, r , the inequality $\text{TVD}(p, q) \leq \text{TVD}(p, r) + \text{TVD}(r, q)$ holds. This implies that the semantic importance score D_t , defined as the difference between two TVDs, is bounded above by the total distance between class centroids:

$$D_t \leq \text{TVD}(\mu_+, \mu_-) = \delta. \quad (8)$$

This upper bound enables threshold sweeping to be performed over a compact and theoretically justified range $\tau \in [-\delta, \delta]$,

Fig. 2. Average PMF distributions over top-level codebook indices for samples with and without ships in the maritime dataset. The total variation distance between the class-average PMFs is $\delta = 0.6516$.

improving the tractability of optimization. In our experiments, this upper bound was empirically measured as $\delta = \text{TVD}(\mu_+, \mu_-) = 0.6516$, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Based on this importance score, a binary transmission decision is made using a threshold τ . The transmission decision is determined by an indicator function:

$$\mathbb{I}_t = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } D_t \leq \tau, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

While the semantic importance score D_t provides a principled and effective basis for selective transmission, it does not perfectly capture the uncertainty associated with semantic importance. In practice, there may be overlaps in the D_t values of important and unimportant samples, leading to ambiguous cases near the threshold. To better account for this uncertainty, we empirically estimate the posterior probability that a given image x_t is semantically important, given its score D_t , and utilize this probability in the threshold optimization process.

Since ground-truth labels are unavailable at inference time, it is crucial to infer semantic importance in a label-free and communication-independent manner. To this end, we leverage the semantic importance score D_t , which is computed directly from the input image x_t using the device-side encoder and the shared codebook statistics. This choice ensures that the semantic importance-based decision can be made locally at the IoT or edge device without requiring any feedback or updates from the remote server.

To enable probabilistic reasoning based on D_t , we estimate the posterior probability $p(D_t)$ using labeled validation data, where the labels indicate the presence or absence of semantically important content. Empirical analysis reveals that the relationship between D_t and the likelihood of semantic importance is well approximated by a sigmoid function:

$$p(D_t) \approx \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-k(D_t - \tau))}, \quad (10)$$

where the fitted parameters are $k = -12.405$ and $\tau = 0.0631$. This function is obtained through logistic regression on the validation set, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The fitted curve captures the probabilistic distribution of semantic importance and is later used to estimate the semantic omission risk in the threshold optimization process.

Fig. 3. Empirical sigmoid curve fitted to the semantic importance score D_t using labeled validation data. The curve approximates the probability that a given sample is semantically meaningful.

B. Performance Metrics

To evaluate the effectiveness of selective transmission, we define three key metrics: transmission rate, semantic retention, and semantic validity. These metrics quantify how well the system balances semantic preservation and communication efficiency.

The **transmission rate** $P_{tx}(\tau)$ is defined as the expected fraction of samples selected for transmission:

$$P_{tx}(\tau) = \mathbb{E}_{x_t} [\mathbb{I}_{\{D_t \leq \tau\}}]. \quad (11)$$

The **semantic retention** $R(\tau)$ is the fraction of semantically important samples that are transmitted:

$$R(\tau) = \mathbb{P}(D_t \leq \tau | x_t \in \mathcal{S}_+), \quad (12)$$

where \mathcal{S}_+ denotes the set of samples that contain critical semantic content (e.g., ships).

The **semantic validity** $V(\tau)$ is the probability that a transmitted sample is semantically important:

$$V(\tau) = \mathbb{P}(x_t \in \mathcal{S}_+ | D_t \leq \tau). \quad (13)$$

These metrics are interdependent and vary with the threshold τ . A lower threshold typically increases semantic validity but may reduce retention by omitting important content. Conversely, a higher threshold improves retention at the cost of transmitting more irrelevant samples. Selecting τ involves balancing these competing objectives based on system priorities.

In the next section, we describe how the optimal threshold τ is determined using an empirically guided Lagrangian formulation.

IV. THRESHOLD OPTIMIZATION

A. Formulation of the Optimization Problem

To balance semantic retention and communication efficiency, we formulate a constrained optimization problem that prioritizes the transmission of semantically important samples while avoiding excessive redundancy. The objective is to

Fig. 4. Trade-off between semantic retention and semantic validity as a function of the semantic omission budget λ_{budget} . Increasing the budget allows more aggressive filtering, improving transmission efficiency at the cost of missed semantic content.

minimize the cumulative importance scores of the transmitted samples, subject to a constraint on the total omission risk:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\tau} \quad & \sum_{t=1}^T D_t \cdot \mathbb{I}_{\{D_t \leq \tau\}} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{I}_{\{D_t > \tau\}} \cdot p(D_t) \leq \lambda_{\text{budget}}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $p(D_t)$ is the estimated probability that sample t is semantically important and λ_{budget} represents the maximum allowable omission risk. Fig. 4 illustrates the trade-off between semantic retention and validity as the omission budget increases.

To enable efficient optimization, we apply a Lagrangian relaxation of the constrained problem:

$$\mathcal{L}(\tau) = \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{I}_{\{D_t \leq \tau\}} \cdot D_t + \mu \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{I}_{\{D_t > \tau\}} \cdot p(D_t), \quad (15)$$

where $\mu > 0$ is the Lagrange multiplier that balances compact transmission (by minimizing retained distances) against semantic risk (by penalizing omitted important samples).

B. Optimization Procedure and Results

By the triangle inequality of total variation distance, the semantic importance score D_t is upper bounded by $\delta = \text{TVD}(\mu_+, \mu_-)$, measured as $\delta = 0.6516$ in our evaluation. This bounds the search space to $\tau \in [-\delta, \delta]$, enabling tractable grid search. For each candidate threshold, we evaluate $\mathcal{L}(\tau)$ and select the minimizer:

$$\tau^* = \arg \min_{\tau \in [-\delta, \delta]} \mathcal{L}(\tau). \quad (16)$$

Varying the threshold τ controls the trade-off between semantic retention and communication compactness: larger values lead to more conservative selection with higher semantic retention $R(\tau)$, while smaller values favor more aggressive filtering, resulting in higher semantic validity $V(\tau)$. This trade-off is illustrated in Fig. 5. At $\tau = 0.444$, the system achieves 93.3% semantic validity, 84.9% retention, and a reduced transmission rate of 45.5%. These results demonstrate that the relaxed formulation effectively identifies an operating point

Fig. 5. Variation of semantic retention, semantic validity, and transmission rate with respect to the threshold τ . The curves illustrate the trade-off between preserving important samples and reducing transmission volume.

that balances low communication cost with minimal semantic loss.

V. NUMERICAL EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

We evaluate the proposed semantic communication framework on the Singapore Maritime Dataset, which contains maritime surveillance images consisting of ships, sea, and sky under diverse visual conditions. The dataset is split into 80% for training and 20% for validation. A custom image loader is implemented to support unstructured folder structures, and all images are normalized using standard preprocessing.

The semantic encoder is implemented using a hierarchical (top, bottom) VQ-VAE-2 model. The model is configured with a codebook size $K = 512$, embedding dimension $D = 64$, and convolutional channel width of 128. Each encoder comprises two residual blocks. The training objective combines SSIM loss and a latent commitment loss (with weight 0.25). Optimization is performed using Adam with cosine annealing and warm-up, where the learning rate decays from 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} over 10,000 updates.

To isolate the effect of semantic compression and selective transmission, all training and reconstruction quality evaluations are conducted under an ideal communication environment without channel noise. This setup allows us to focus purely on the semantic aspects of the model performance without interference from physical-layer distortions.

For latency evaluation, we incorporate a wireless channel model with Rayleigh fading and a fixed bandwidth of $W = 10$ MHz. In addition, encoding and decoding latencies are empirically measured on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU and included in the overall latency computation.

B. Quantitative Evaluation of Semantic Selection

1) *Metric Trends under Varying Thresholds*: To evaluate the impact of the threshold parameter τ on system performance, we conduct a grid search over the theoretically justified interval $\tau \in [-\delta, \delta]$, where $\delta = \text{TVD}(\mu_+, \mu_-) = 0.6516$. For each candidate τ , we compute the semantic retention $R(\tau)$, semantic validity $V(\tau)$, and expected transmission rate $P_{\text{tx}}(\tau)$.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE OF BASELINE METHODS

Method	PSNR (dB)	SSIM	Data Size (KB)
JPEG (Q=50)	34.43	0.9072	5.49
Deep JSCC	31.88	0.9274	4.00
VQ-VAE	32.13	0.9094	0.92
Proposed	32.54	0.9092	0.42

Fig. 5 illustrates the trade-off behavior among these metrics. As τ increases, the system becomes more permissive, preserving more semantically important samples (higher $R(\tau)$), but also allowing more irrelevant transmissions (lower $V(\tau)$) and increased transmission rate.

2) *Lagrangian Optimization and Optimal Point*: We apply the Lagrangian relaxation strategy proposed in Section IV and evaluate its effectiveness through grid-based threshold optimization. As shown in the prior analysis, increasing the penalty coefficient μ results in more conservative transmission with higher semantic retention, while lower μ prioritizes compactness.

In our experiments, we found that the optimal trade-off was achieved when the penalty coefficient was set to $\mu = 0.444$, which corresponded to a threshold value of $\tau^* = 0.0868$. At this operating point, the system achieved a semantic validity of 93.3%, a semantic retention of 84.9%, and a transmission rate of 45.5%. These results confirm that the Lagrangian formulation successfully identifies a well-balanced operating point that effectively manages the trade-off between semantic preservation and communication efficiency under resource constraints.

C. Comparison with Baseline Methods

We first evaluate three baseline image transmission methods—JPEG (Q=50), Deep JSCC ($k/n=1/12$), and VQ-VAE—in terms of reconstruction quality and data size. As summarized in Table I, VQ-VAE provides a favorable trade-off between PSNR and semantic compactness, reducing data size by an order of magnitude compared to JPEG and Deep JSCC.

We then compare the proposed selective transmission framework with the base VQ-VAE model. As shown in Table II, our method achieves comparable PSNR and SSIM while reducing the average semantic data size by more than 50%. Although the transmission rate is not explicitly shown, only 45.5% of samples are transmitted on average, significantly lowering communication overhead.

To quantify the overall communication efficiency, we measure the total latency for each method by combining the computational and transmission delays. Specifically, we incorporate the measured encoding and decoding times (average wall-time) into the latency calculation, along with the expected transmission delay over a Rayleigh fading channel.

For the VQ-VAE-based methods, we use the actual average encoding and decoding latencies measured on GPU—0.83 ms and 0.57 ms per image, respectively. The transmission delay

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON: VQ-VAE VS OURS

Method	PSNR (dB)	SSIM	Data Size (KB)
VQ-VAE	32.13	0.9094	0.92
Proposed	32.54	0.9092	0.42

is estimated based on the data size and channel throughput, assuming a Rayleigh fading channel with exponentially distributed gains.

Figure 6 shows the resulting latency comparison across various SNR values. While JPEG and Deep JSCC methods transmit every image regardless of content, our method selectively transmits semantically important samples, significantly reducing both the average data size and the associated delay. As the figure shows, our method consistently achieves the lowest end-to-end latency across all SNR levels, highlighting its advantage in bandwidth-constrained communication environments.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a semantic importance-based selective image transmission framework tailored for bandwidth-constrained environments. By leveraging a hierarchical VQ-VAE-2 model and quantized latent representations, our system achieves efficient semantic compression by transmitting only the codebook indices. Furthermore, we introduced a selective transmission mechanism based on total variation distance (TVD) and a Lagrangian optimization framework to identify an optimal threshold that balances semantic retention $R(\tau)$ and validity $V(\tau)$.

Experimental results on the Singapore Maritime Dataset demonstrate that the proposed method achieves high semantic validity (93.3%) and semantic retention (84.9%) while reducing the transmission rate by 54.5%. Compared to baseline methods such as JPEG and VQ-VAE, our approach maintains comparable image reconstruction quality (PSNR: 32.54dB, SSIM: 0.9092) with significantly lower transmission latency.

While the Lagrangian formulation provides a principled solution for threshold selection, we also present a practical alternative for real-world deployment. In time-sensitive applications, the threshold can be selected by fixing a desired semantic retention level (e.g., 80%) and consulting the pre-computed $R(\tau)$ curve. This allows the system to adapt flexibly to application-specific priorities without runtime optimization overhead.

Future work will focus on extending the system to more realistic settings by incorporating physical-layer channel models such as AWGN and Rayleigh fading, and evaluating the system performance under noisy transmission conditions. Another important direction is to develop an adaptive transmission mechanism that leverages the hierarchical structure of the VQ-VAE codebooks: depending on the channel state, the system can selectively transmit the top-level, bottom-level, or both latent codes. Such a strategy would further improve communication

Fig. 6. Average total latency vs. SNR under Rayleigh fading. Encoding and decoding times are included for VQ-VAE-based methods.

efficiency by allocating resources based on channel quality, enabling dynamic adaptation to varying network conditions.

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